

Students' performance in English: effects of teachers' leadership behavior and students' motivation

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ABSTRACT

The research was conducted to determine how the leadership behavior of English teachers affects students' performance in the language and to examine how the motivation of students toward English language learning influences the relationship between the leadership behavior of teachers and the performance of their students in the language. The statistical tools used in this descriptive research study were frequency analysis, mean computation, correlation analysis, regression analysis, and mediation analysis. As the students perceive, their English teacher's manifest leadership behavior consideration more than initiating structure. Results have shown that the students scored higher in integrative than in instrumental motivation. Both dimensions of leadership behavior positively relate to the students' integrative and instrumental motivation and English performance. This indicates that they will be motivated to learn and perform better in English no matter what dimension of leadership behavior teachers will manifest. However, regression analyses have shown different results. While integrative motivation is positively and significantly correlated to students' performance in English, instrumental motivation is not. Instrumental and integrative motivation do not mediate the effects of initiating structure on students' English performance. However, both forms of motivation significantly mediate the effect of consideration on students' English performance.

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1. INTRODUCTION

Teachers are at the forefront of the educational process and are in direct control of teaching-learning activities that comprise the bulk of that process. It is, therefore, imperative that they possess, aside from the required academic qualifications, the necessary knowledge, skills, and values to effectively carry out the said activities and perform their other pedagogical functions. Much has been said about teachers' required qualifications, knowledge, skills, and values to succeed. Nevertheless, one particular skill has not been given enough attention-leadership. Teachers are usually looked upon as overseers of the teaching-learning process, not much (or not at all) as leaders who do something in the classroom beyond teaching. Teachers do not just teach; they also lead. They perform teaching and leading at the same time. Teaching leadership is a key factor that helps students learn and flourish [1]. Part of what a teacher does professionally is leading. Teachers are inherently leaders. They would not be able to effectively facilitate learning, perform classroom management, and mentor their students if they are not. The diversity of roles teachers undertake makes them leaders, and the implementation of their leadership responsibilities is referred to as teacher leadership.

Studies have shown that teachers' leadership behaviors substantially affect students' academic performance. One such study reveals that students taught by teacher leaders have a high probability of succeeding academically [2]. Another study found that classroom leadership has a positive relationship with academic results, behavior management, and many other things [3]. Leadership and what teachers teach in the classroom are inseparable, making its exercise not optional but mandatory. Teacher leaders could effectively facilitate learning, resulting in better student performance. One study concluded that a teacher's leadership style contributes immensely to the success of teaching and learning in schools [4]. It is hypothesized in this study that the brand of leadership that English teachers exercise when teaching the language could help students improve their performance in English, leading them to develop proficiency in the language. Their pedagogical functions require that they not only deliver the lessons but also lead the students in the learning process and motivate them to participate actively in discussions and perform better academically. Motivating students is an integral part of the teaching-learning process. Experts explained that cultivating student motivation is a complex but necessary aspect of teaching [5]. Teachers may have encountered students who are either engaged, motivated, and excited to learn or distracted, disinterested, and reluctant to engage. That is the kind of challenge teachers face. If teachers wish to perform effectively in a language classroom, they must possess qualities in their teaching practices, including rapport, passion, flexibility, balance, and purpose [6].

Teaching the language is an extra challenge for teachers who teach English to Korean students. It is a difficult challenge because their Korean students have varying levels of English proficiency, and English is also a foreign language to them. However, aside from the differences in the student's English proficiency levels, teachers must overcome a cultural barrier. It is trickier to lead and motivate a group of students whose culture differs from theirs.

For whatever instructional activities teachers design, the primary objective is for the students to learn. However, learning is not a one-way traffic. No matter how pedagogically skillful a teacher is, there will be no learning if the students do not share. No matter how good a leader a teacher is, learning objectives will only be met if the students are willing to participate in the process. Making the students learn is not the sole responsibility of the teacher. The students need to exert effort. They must want to learn. Motivation comes not just from the teacher but also from the students themselves. A study affirmed that motivation and learning experiences are critical in determining cognitive learning outcomes [7]. That study provides insight into the impact of motivation and learning experiences on students' cognitive learning outcomes. A review of literature and studies related to motivation and language acquisition highlighted the significance of student motivation in learning English in the successful acquisition of skills in the language. Motivation has been considered and widely recognized as an important component in successfully learning and acquiring a second or foreign language [8].

For students for whom English is either a second or a foreign language, performing well in the said language is a task that is easier said than done. To acquire the skills in the language, they need to have the desire to learn. While their English teachers should be able to motivate them to learn, they need to have the motivation towards English language learning. Learning objectives will only be attained or challenged if teachers manifest the appropriate leadership behavior necessary for their attainment if the students are willing to engage. Language competence and psychological factors were factored into investigating why students performed poorly in speaking English. Studies support that motivation to learn English (or the lack of it) significantly impacts performance in English [9], [10].

Both motivations toward English language learning and the leadership behavior of teachers are believed to play a vital role in improving students' academic performance in English. The constructs-leadership behavior of teachers, motivation in learning English, and performance of students in English are the variables investigated in this study. Leadership behaviors of teachers are classified into consideration and initiating structure, while motivation toward English language learning is categorized as integrative and instrumental.

Teacher-related variables have always been considered determinants of students' academic performance. While the students themselves contribute to their success through having the needed motivation to learn, even having that proper motivation can be affected by their teachers. Examining how teachers lead their students in the learning process and how they affect the motivation of the students to learn will be guided by the four-factor model of teacher leadership theory. The said model was proposed by Angelle and DeHart [11]. Two of the four factors in the model that bear significance in this study are sharing expertise (SE) and supra-practicer (SP). The first focuses on the teachers' pedagogical and classroom management skills, and the second on their willingness to go above and beyond their prescribed roles.

The investigation of students' motivation to learn English was examined using two different theories: the expectancy-value theory for instrumental motivation and Albert Bandura's social cognitive theory for integrative motivation. The expectancy-value theory describes the relationship between a student's expectancy for success at a task or achieving a goal and the value of task completion or goal attainment [12]. Particular academic studies and achievements valued by the students would reveal a more substantial effect of expectancy

on their learning behavior [13]. On the other hand, the social cognitive theory posits that learning occurs via observation and modeling and those targeted behaviors are the product of correlations between personal, behavioral, and environmental factors. Studies confirmed that this theory can be used to inform practices that successfully assist in learning English [14].

This study was conducted for the following purposes: to determine how the leadership behavior English teachers display in the classroom affects students' performance in English and to examine how the motivation of students toward English language learning influences the relationship between the leadership behaviors of teachers and the performance of students in their English course. The timing for this study cannot be any better for teacher leadership, which may be commonly discussed in educational research and practice. However, the relationship between this construct and student achievement has not been soundly established by empirical evidence [15]. This implies a need for more research on the relationship between the said constructs. A group of researchers highlighted the need for such studies to explore teacher's leadership role in students' performance [16]. Additionally, contrasting findings on whether students are integratively motivated to learn English or instrumentally motivated represent a disagreement gap. Studies conducted to investigate the motivation of students to learn the language produced inconclusive results, with some concluding that students have higher integrative motivation [17], [18] and some revealing that they are more integratively motivated [19], [20]. The main objectives of this study are the examination of the effects of leadership behaviors of English teachers on the performance of students in English courses and the investigation of the mediating effects of instrumental motivation and integrative motivation on the influence of the leadership behaviors of English teachers on student's performance in English courses.

The general problem of this study is: How does motivation to learn English mediate the relationship between teachers' leadership behaviors and students' performance in English courses? Specifically, this study sought answers to the following questions: i) What are the leadership behaviors of teachers in terms of consideration and initiating structure?; ii) What is the motivation of students in learning English in terms of instrumental motivation and integrative motivation?; iii) What is the level of students' performance in their English course?; iv) Are there significant relationships between the leadership behaviors of teachers, the motivation of students in learning English, and the performance of students in their English course?; and v) Do the instrumental motivation and integrative motivation of students mediate the relationship between the teachers' leadership behaviors and students' performance in their English course?

2. METHOD

The descriptive survey research technique was used in this study. This study investigated the relationship between teachers' leadership behaviors and students' English course performance. The investigation further explored how their motivation in learning English mediates that relationship.

2.1. Participants

Nine hundred-eleven students from a university in South Korea served as respondents. They belong to the university's different academic departments, are members of different courses, and are enrolled in mandatory English classes. The students who served as respondents in this study were chosen using the purposive sampling method. The classes where they belong were previously identified. The survey was done online, and the participation of the students belonging to the classes purposively chosen, as they were previously informed, was voluntary.

2.2. Data collection

The questionnaire used to gather data needed was divided into the following parts: Part I (profile of respondents), which was intended to establish the demographic profile of the student-respondents; Part II-A (teacher leadership behavior), which was designed to determine which dimension of leadership behaviors the English teachers exhibit-consideration or initiating structure; Parts II-B (instrumental motivation); and Part II-C (integrative motivation) which were included to measure the level of motivation of students in learning English; and Part III (English grammar proficiency test) was designed to measure the performance of students in English courses.

The items for Part II-A were taken from the leadership behavior description questionnaire (LBDQ) developed by Ohio State University [21]. At the same time, those for Parts II-B and II-C were adapted from the original attitude/motivation test battery (AMTB) designed by Gardner [22]. Part III of the questionnaire was adapted from an instrument created by Fajardo [23]. It is subdivided into the following areas of English grammar proficiency: vocabulary, correct grammatical form, answering questions, combining sentences, and word sequencing.

2.3. Data analysis

There are three constructs whose relationships were investigated in this study. They are students' motivation, teachers' leadership behaviors, and students' academic performance. The main objective of this study is to examine the mediating effects of instrumental and integrative motivation among students on the relationship between the leadership behaviors of their teachers and their performance in English courses.

All data gathered through the questionnaires were treated using frequency counts and means. The student-respondents evaluated their motivation level and their teachers' leadership behaviors. The 5-point scale Likert-scale shown in Table 1 was adapted from the Likert-scale format of Gardner's attitude/motivation battery [22] and was used to determine the student's level of motivation. The corresponding interpretation is indicated opposite the scale. The students' academic performance was measured through the results of their achievement tests in math, science, and English.

Table 1. Descriptive interpretation for student motivation

Scale	Mean Range	Score Range	Motivational Level
5	Strongly Agree	4.50-5.00	Very High
4	Agree	3.50-4.49	High
3	Neither Agree nor Disagree	2.50-3.49	Average
2	Disagree	1.50-2.49	Low
1	Strongly Disagree	1.00-1.49	Very Low

The performance of students in English was measured through a grammar test. Their total scores were used in the correlation and regression analyses. A separate statistical analysis of how the students performed in five areas of grammar proficiency was also performed. The mean scores of the student respondents were computed, and the scale shown in Table 2 was used to determine their level of proficiency in each area. It was adapted from the Likert-scale used in a study that examined the English proficiency level of students [24].

Table 2. Descriptive interpretation for students' level of English proficiency

Score Range	Level of Proficiency
4.50-5.00	Highly Proficient
3.50-4.49	Very Proficient
2.50-3.49	Proficient
1.50-2.49	Moderately Proficient
1.00-1.49	Less Proficient

The relationship between the leadership behavior of teachers, the motivation of students to learn English, and the performance of students in English were estimated using a correlation coefficient. Regression analyses were performed to test the significant association between the variables. All statistical analyses in the study were done using the SPSS software program. The mediation analysis was performed using the process procedure for SPSS (Version 4.2 Beta) introduced by Hayes [25]. All items used to measure the identified constructs were tested for reliability. The value of the Cronbach alpha should be between the range of 0.70~0.99. There was no common method bias (CMB), with its value being less than 50%.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

There were three constructs whose relationships were investigated in this study. This study investigated the relationship between the leadership behaviors of teachers and the student's performance in their English courses. The investigation further explored how their motivation in learning English mediates that relationship.

3.1. Leadership behavior of teachers

As articulated in the LBDQ manual, consideration refers to the behavior of leaders indicative of friendship, mutual trust, respect, and warmth in a relationship. Conversely, initiating structure indicates a leader's tendency to delineate the relationship between them and those they lead. Leaders strong in dimension consideration are people-oriented, while those leaning towards the other dimension-initiating structure are task-oriented [26]. Teachers who are strong in the consideration dimension are considered student-oriented. Teachers can be perceived to manifest one of the two leadership behaviors, but this does not mean they can no longer show the characteristics of the other.

Teachers need to hone not only their pedagogical skills but also their leadership qualities. A positive relationship exists between the perceived leadership behavior of teachers and student classroom motivation. A study found that the leadership behavior of classroom teachers significantly impacts students' academic success. It added that the democratic leadership behavior displayed by class teachers is the most popular among students and is helpful to student academic achievement [27].

Tables 3 and 4 show the leadership behaviors of foreign English teachers as perceived by their students. For the description and analysis of the leadership behaviors of foreign teachers teaching English to the student-respondents, the LBDQ was used. The LBDQ was designed to measure two dimensions of leadership behaviors: initiating structure and consideration. The perceived leadership behavior of the English teachers in terms of initiating structure is presented in Table 3. The computed mean value of 4.06 implies that the student-respondents perceived that their English teachers manifest, on most occasions, the qualities corresponding to the leadership behavior classified as initiating structure.

Table 3. Distribution of students by perceived initiating structure behavior of teachers

Initiating Structure	Frequency	Percent
4.50-5.00 (Very High)	249	27.33
3.50-4.49 (High)	515	56.53
2.50-3.49 (Moderate)	128	14.05
1.50-2.49 (Low)	13	1.43
1.00-1.49 (Very Low)	6	0.66
Total	911	27.33

Table 4 shows the perceived leadership behavior of the English teachers in terms of consideration. The participants in this study observed that on most occasions, the foreign teachers teaching them English show the qualities attributed to the leadership behavior known as consideration. The computed means signify that the foreign teachers show more leadership qualities, called consideration, rather than initiating structure.

Table 4. Distribution of students by perceived initiating structure behavior of teachers

Consideration	Frequency	Percent
4.50-5.00 (Very High)	405	44.46
3.50-4.49 (High)	396	43.47
2.50-3.49 (Moderate)	90	9.88
1.50-2.49 (Low)	13	1.43
1.00-1.49 (Very Low)	7	0.77
Total	911	100.00

3.2. Motivation of student in learning English

This section presents the students' perceptions of their level of motivation in learning English. Gardner's attitude/motivation test battery, where the motivation for learning a language is dichotomized into instrumental and integrative motivation, was used. This study looks into two categories of motivation to learn the English language among students: instrumental and integrative. When Gardner developed the AMTB, he explained that instrumentally motivated learners desire to acquire a second language for external rewards that may include recognition, appraisal, and personal fulfillment, while those who are motivated integratively do so for them to understand the people who speak the language better. The computed means of 3.55 and 3.96, shown in Tables 5 and 6, indicate that the students are highly motivated to learn English. The higher mean score (3.96) for integrative motivation indicates that students are more integratively than instrumentally motivated.

Table 5. Distribution of students by instrumental motivation

Instrumental motivation	Frequency	Percent
4.50-5.00 (Very High)	24	2.63
3.50-4.49 (High)	506	55.54
2.50-3.49 (Moderate)	364	39.96
1.50-2.49 (Low)	16	1.76
1.00-1.49 (Very Low)	1	0.11
Total	911	100.00

Motivation impacts the rate and success of foreign language learning because it tends to compensate for language proficiency and learning deficiencies. Integrative motivation drives students to learn English as they recognize the vital role of the English language in global communication and desire to visit English-speaking regions worldwide [28]. Integrative motivation is a type of inspiration that each learner has. That includes the desire to become more fluent language users, communicate more effectively with foreigners, and enjoy participating in culturally diverse outdoor activities [29]. Most reviewed studies and literature on motivation to learn English indicate that more students are driven by instrumental motivation in learning English. The students' tendency towards instrumental motivation could be explained by their focus on securing jobs that require English proficiency or acquiring a certificate of English to get through specific academic requirements [30].

Table 6. Distribution of students by integrative motivation

Integrative motivation	Frequency	Percent
4.50-5.00 (Very High)	312	34.25
3.50-4.49 (High)	361	39.63
2.50-3.49 (Moderate)	194	21.30
1.50-2.49 (Low)	31	3.40
1.00-1.49 (Very Low)	13	1.43
Total	911	100.00

3.3. Performance of students in English course

The performance of students in English was measured using a 25-item grammar test. The said test was subdivided into the following areas of English grammar proficiency: correct grammatical form, answering questions, combining sentences, and word sequencing. As shown in Table 7, most scores are clustered in the center, and the distribution is considered normal. 542 out of 911 student-respondents got scores of 12 and higher, and 369 got 11 or lower. Four hundred thirty-one students who participated in the study had scores ranging from 9 to 14. Generally speaking, based on these scores, the students performed well in the English grammar test. Table 8 shows students' performance in specific areas of English grammar proficiency. The student-respondents are proficient in vocabulary, correct grammatical form, and answering questions. They are moderately proficient in combining sentences and word sequencing. They scored the highest in answering questions and lowest in combining sentences, with mean scores of 3.49 and 1.70, respectively. Aggregately, their mean score is 2.56.

Table 7. Distribution of students by score in English

Score	Frequency	Percent
21-23	23	2.52
18-20	106	11.64
15-17	195	21.41
12-14	218	23.93
9-11	213	23.38
6-8	127	13.94
3-5	28	3.07
0-2	1	0.11
Total	911	100.00

Table 8. Performance of students in certain areas of English proficiency

Scores	Vocabulary		Correct Grammatical Form		Answering Questions		Combining Sentences		Word Sequencing	
	F	%	F	%	F	%	F	%	F	%
5	22	2.41	114	12.51	297	32.60	27	2.96	35	3.84
4	221	24.26	188	20.64	233	25.58	65	7.14	86	9.44
3	354	38.86	197	21.62	140	15.37	123	13.50	191	20.97
2	235	25.80	218	23.93	131	14.38	218	23.93	219	24.04
1	66	7.24	148	16.25	77	8.45	347	38.09	293	32.16
0	13	1.43	46	5.05	33	3.62	131	14.38	87	9.55
Total	911	100.00	911	100.00	911	100.00	911	100.00	911	100.00
Mean/Interpretation	2.85/Proficient		2.74/Proficient		3.49/Proficient		1.70/Moderately Proficient		2.00/Moderately Proficient	
Overall Mean: 2.56. Interpretation: Proficient										

3.4. Relationships between the leadership behaviors of teachers, motivation of students, and the performance of students in English course

The results of the correlation analysis shown in Table 9 indicate that initiating structure is positively and significantly correlated with instrumental motivation ($r=.340$, $p<0.01$), integrative motivation ($r=.517$, $p<0.01$), and leadership behavior ($r=.158$, $p<0.01$). Consideration is positively and significantly correlated with instrumental motivation ($r=.352$, $p<0.01$), integrative motivation ($r=.569$, $p<0.01$), and the performance of students in English ($r=.185$, $p<0.01$). Instrumental motivation is not significantly correlated with the performance of students in English ($r=.002$, $p>0.05$), while integrative motivation is positively and significantly correlated with the performance of students in English ($r=.166$, $p<0.01$).

Table 9. Correlations among the dependent, independent, and mediating variables

Variables	PSE	LB-IS	LB-C	M-Ins M	M-Int. M
PSE	1				
LB-IS	.158**	1			
LB-C	.185**	.903**	1		
M-Ins M	.002	.340**	.352**	1	
M-Int. M	.166**	.517**	.569**	.359**	1

** Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

* Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

PSE-Performance of Students in English IV, LB-IS- Leadership Behavior-Initiating Structure, LB-C-Leadership Behavior-Consideration, M-Ins. M-Instrumental Motivation, M-Int. M-Integrative Motivation

“Teacher leadership plays a significant role in improving the global education system.” The preceding statement is one of the significant assertions made in a study conducted in Sweden. The Swedish education system, in particular, the leadership teachers exercise in the classroom is critical to delivering the English language. Results of the study have shown that no specific types of leadership styles can help deliver instructions in their schools [31]. The leadership type depends on the prevailing situation and group of students. However, it was mentioned in the study that specific strategies teachers use that resemble methods applied by teachers whose leadership behavior is strong on the consideration dimension include being calm, kind, collaborative, and passionate, creating a positive relationship with the students, and treating them fairly and respectfully.

The positive correlation between integrative motivation and students' English performance confirms the argument in a study that casts fresh light on the motivation factors that may drive English as a foreign language (EFL) learning. The study found that integrative motivation is among those factors that inspire students to exert efforts toward learning English [32]. In an examination of students' motivation in learning English, it was discovered that students are more instrumentally motivated than integratively motivated in the English as a second language (ESL) learning process. Such is considered a significant finding. The researchers found that instrumentally motivated students do not commit much to their English language learning. Compared to integratively motivated students, they cannot commit their time and energy to learning. They recommended that students must be motivated integratively so that they will learn the language proactively, continue learning English during after-school English classes, and enjoy the learning process by not seeing it as an extra burden to their study [33].

3.5. Mediating effects of instrumental and integrative motivation (parallel mediation analysis)

The mediation analysis was performed on students' performance in the English course as the dependent variable, initiating structure and consideration as independent variables and covariates, and instrumental motivation and integrative motivation as the mediating variables using the process procedure for SPSS Version 4.2 beta written by Hayes [25]. Since the study includes two moderating variables, the parallel mediation model was applied to the data. Moreover, the process macro allows for a single predictor variable only. Thus, the study runs two separate models for each predictor and switches the role of variables as covariates. The results of the analyses are summarized as shown in Tables 10-14.

The regression equation in Table 10 appears significant with $F=16.2936$ and $p=.0000$. With an R square of .1861. The combined variables explain 19% of the variation in students' total scores. A closer look reveals that of the two leadership behaviors of the teachers, only consideration behavior appears to have a significant coefficient ($p=.0025$). The positive coefficient of 1.4468 of consideration means that for every unit increase or decrease in the level of consideration, there will be a 1.45 unit increase or decrease in student performance in the English course.

Table 10. Regression of students' performance in English on initiating structure and consideration

Independent Variables	Coefficient	P	R ²	F	Significance of F
Initiating structure	-.3607	.5070	.1861	16.2936	.0000
Consideration	1.4468	.0025			

Hypothesis 1a. Initiating structure has a significant effect on student performance. (Not supported)

Hypothesis 2a. Consideration has a significant effect on student performance. (Supported)

The regression equation in Table 11 appears significant with $F=65.7266$ and $p=.0000$. With an R square of .3556. The combined variables explain 36% of students' instrumental motivation variation. A closer look reveals that of the two leadership behaviors of the teachers, only consideration behavior appears to have a significant coefficient ($p=.0009$). The positive coefficient of .1724 of consideration means that for every unit increase or decrease in the level of consideration, there will be a 1.7 unit increase or decrease in student instrumental motivation in the English course.

Table 11. Regression of instrumental motivation on initiating structure and consideration

Independent Variables	Coefficient	P	R ²	F	Significance of F
Initiating structure	.1001	.0900	.3556	65.7266	.0000
Consideration	.1724	.0009			

Hypothesis 1b. Initiating structure has a significant effect on instrumental motivation. (Not supported)

Hypothesis 2b. Consideration has a significant effect on instrumental motivation. (Supported)

The regression equation in Table 12 appears significant with $F=217.2471$ and $p=.0000$. With an R square of .5689. The combined variables explain 36% of students' integrative motivation variation. A closer look reveals that of the two leadership behaviors of the teachers, only consideration behavior appears to have a significant coefficient ($p=.0000$). The positive coefficient of .7048 of consideration means that for every unit increase or decrease in the level of consideration, there will be .7 unit increase or decrease in student integrative motivation in English course.

Table 12. Regression of integrative motivation on initiating structure and consideration

Independent Variables	Coefficient	p	R ²	F	Significance of F
Initiating structure	.0230	.8030	.5689	217.2471	.0000
Consideration	.7048	.0000			

Hypothesis 1c. Initiating structure has a significant effect on integrative motivation. (Not supported)

Hypothesis 2c. Consideration has a significant effect on integrative motivation. (Supported)

The regression equation in Table 13 appears significant with $F=11.1720$ and $p=.0000$. With an R square of .2168. The combined variables explain 22% of students' total score variation. Holding the other variables constant, the results show the effect of each variable on the student performance with the total score as the indicator. A closer look reveals that of the two leadership behaviors of the teachers, only consideration behavior appears to have a significant coefficient ($p=.0159$). The positive coefficient of 1.1964 of consideration means that for every unit increase or decrease in the level of consideration, there will be 12-unit increases or decreases in student instrumental motivation in English courses. The students' instrumental and integrative motivation coefficients appear significant (.0107 and .0059, respectively). The negative significant coefficient of instrumental motivation of -.7947 indicates that for every unit increase in instrumental motivation, there will be a .79 unit decrease in student total score. There will be a .79 increase in students' instrumental motivation for every unit decrease in instrumental motivation. On the other hand, the positive coefficient of .5497 of integrative motivation means that for every unit increase or decrease in the level of integrative motivation, there will be a .55 unit increase or decrease in student integrative motivation in the English course.

Table 13. Regression of total score on initiating structure, consideration, instrumental motivation, and integrative motivation

Independent and Moderating Variables	Coefficient	p	R ²	F	Significance of F
Initiating structure	-.2938	.5874	.2168	11.1720	.0000
Consideration	1.1964	.0159			
Instrumental	-.7947	.0107			
Integrative	.5497	.0059			

Using the data for the study, the process assessed the mediating effects of instrumental motivation and integrative motivation on the relationships between the independent variables, viz., initiating structure and consideration, and the dependent variable, namely the students' total score in the English test. The results shown in Table 14 indicate that both the indirect effects of instrumental and integrative motivation appear insignificant. Hence, they do not have significant mediation effects between initiating structure and total score. On the other hand, the effect of consideration on the total score is significantly mediated by both instrumental and integrative motivation, as their indirect effects appear to be both significant. The results show that the direct effect of consideration on total score remains significant in the presence of significant indirect effects, meaning that both instrumental and integrative motivation partially mediate the relationship between the teachers' consideration of leadership behavior and students' performance in English courses. The results show that the mediating effect between instrumental and integrative motivation is $-.5244$, and it is Bootstrap's 95% confidence interval (CI) does not include 0. This means that the mediating effect of integrative motivation is significantly more significant than instrumental motivation in the association between the teachers' consideration of leadership behavior and students' performance in English subjects.

Table 14. Mediating effects of instrumental motivation and integrative motivation in the relationship between initiating structure and consideration and performance of students in English

	Initiating Structure			Consideration		
	Coefficient	p	Remarks	Coefficient	p	Remarks
Total Effect	-.3607	.5070	Not Significant	1.4468	.0025	Significant
Direct effect	-.2938	.5874	Not Significant	1.1964	.0159	Significant
Indirect Effects						
Total	-.0669			.2504		
Instrumental	-.0795	With 0	Not Significant	-.1370	No 0	Significant
Integrative	.0126	With 0	Not significant	.3874	No 0	Significant
CI	-.0922	With 0	Not significant	-.5244	No 0	Significant

Hypothesis 1e. Instrumental motivation significantly mediates the effect of initiating structure on students' performance. (Not supported)
 Hypothesis 2e. Integrative motivation significantly mediates the effect of initiating structure on students' performance. (Not supported)
 Hypothesis 1f. Instrumental motivation significantly mediates the effect of consideration on students' performance. (Supported)
 Hypothesis 2f. Integrative motivation significantly mediates the effect of consideration on students' performance. (Supported)

A study concluded that both dimensions of leadership behavior-initiating structure and consideration positively influence student performance [33]. Task-oriented leaders scoring higher in the initiating structure dimension are considered autocratic. Leaders who focus on tasks that should be carried out to reach goals can be described as autocratic. Conversely, people-oriented leaders who score higher in the consideration dimension are perceived as transformational leaders. Transformational leadership is attached to people-oriented decision-making styles. The study's overall result indicated that transformational leadership and autocratic styles were utilized in the respondent schools more than in other styles. The study revealed that students performed well and that both teachers and students were satisfied with their school administrators, and their performing well is a direct reflection of leadership styles. Figure 1 shows the model paths with regression results on the variables.

Figure 1. The model paths with regression results on the variables

4. CONCLUSION

As perceived by the student-respondents, their English teachers manifest both dimensions of leadership behavior structure and consideration. However, the computed mean scores show that their English teachers manifest consideration more than initiating structure. This perception of the students indicates that their teachers are more student-oriented than task-oriented. The teachers manifesting the leadership behavior consideration more strongly than initiating structure, as perceived by the students, may have contributed to students performing well in English.

The students scored higher in integrative motivation than in instrumental motivation, and this means that students are more integrative motivated. Being integrative motivated indicates that they study the language for intrinsic reasons rather than extrinsic ones. Both dimensions of leadership behavior are positively related to integrative and instrumental motivation and students' performance in English courses, meaning that students will be motivated and perform better in English no matter what dimension of leadership behavior their teachers manifest. Results of this study have shown that the two forms of motivation—integrative and instrumental different effects on students' English performance. While integrative motivation is positively and significantly correlated to students' performance in English, instrumental motivation is not. This positive correlation between integrative motivation and students' English performance means that students become better at the language if they are integrative motivated to learn it. But while correlation analyses have shown that both dimensions of leadership behavior structure and consideration are positively correlated to both instrumental and integrative motivation, the regression equation indicates that only consideration significantly affects both instrumental and integrative motivation, which means that students tend to be more motivated to learn the language both instrumentally and integrative if their teachers manifest the consideration dimension of leadership behavior.

The results of the computations for the mediating effects of instrumental and integrative motivation on the relationship between initiating structure and consideration of students' performance in English courses are consistent with the results of the regression analyses. Instrumental and integrative motivation do not mediate the effects of initiating structure on students' English performance. However, both forms of motivation (instrumental and integrative) significantly mediate the effects of consideration on students' performance in English courses.

5. RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the significant findings and conclusions drawn, certain recommendations are hereby presented. Teachers must remember that aside from teaching, leading is part of what they do professionally. Teachers are leaders at the same time. They need to hone not only their pedagogical skills but also their leadership skills. They must study what leadership behaviors are most effective in helping their students have better academic performance. The review of related literature and studies shows a disagreement gap regarding whether integrative or instrumental motivation results in better learning in English. They offer no conclusive evidence as to which of them is superior. Thus, it is recommended that more studies be done to determine which of the two forms of motivation in learning English is better. However, in this study at least, student-respondents were more integrative and motivated to learn the language. Their reasons for learning English are more intrinsic than extrinsic, not for the sake of academic requirements but for them to be able to interact successfully with people from other cultures should they learn to communicate in English. Therefore, English teachers should try to inculcate among their students the value of studying English not only for the sake of getting good grades but also for the ability to communicate more effectively in the language. Lastly, the results of the mediation analyses show that integrative motivation significantly mediates the effect of the leadership behavior dimension called consideration. Thus, teachers should establish a good rapport with their students while helping them be more integratively motivated to learn English.

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